

1-(N-Acetylamino)-5-n-butyl-7,8-dimethoxy-1,2,3,4-tetrahydronaphthalene (IV : n=3, R₁=H, R₂=COCH₃): It was prepared by the interaction of acetyl chloride with amine and crystallised from dil alcohol (84%), m.p. 135°; ν_{max} (KBr) 3300 (NH), 1650 cm⁻¹ (amide CO).

The following amides were prepared (R₂, % yield, m.p. in the order shown) : COC₈H₅, 71, 125°; COC₈H₇, 70, 110°. The analytical results for these compounds were in good agreement with the calculated values.

1-(5-n-Butyl-7,8-dimethoxy-1,2,3,4-tetrahydronaphthylethylamine (IV : n=3, R₁=H, R₂=C₂H₅): The acetylamino compound (IV : n=3, R₁=H, R₂=COCH₃; 2 g) was reduced with LAH (0.2 g) in dry ether (150 ml) in the usual way to yield the product (1.6 g), b.p. 180°/1.5 mm; ν_{max} (film) 3300 cm⁻¹; picrate (EtOH) m.p. 173°. The following amines (IV) were prepared (R₂, % yield, b.p., m.p. of the picrate in the order shown) : C₂H₅, 76, 165°/0.6 mm, 168°; C₄H₉, 83, 178°/1 mm, 162°. The analytical results for these compounds were in good agreement with the calculated values.

1-(5-n-Butyl-7,8-dimethoxy-1,2,3,4-tetrahydronaphthyl)dimethylamine (IV : n=3; R₁=R₂=CH₃): The amine (IV : n=3, R₁=R₂=H; 1.6 g), formic acid (90%, 1.6 g) and formaldehyde (37%, 1.5 ml) were reacted together in the usual way to yield the amine (1.2 g, 68%), b.p. 170°/1.5 mm. The hydrochloride was crystallised from benzene and petroleum ether (b.p. 60-80°) mixture, m.p. 110°.

The following amines (IV : n=3, R₁=CH₃, R₂) were prepared similarly (R₂, % yield, b.p., m.p. of the hydrochloride in the order shown) : C₂H₅, 66, 240°/1.5 mm, 115° (benzene-petroleum ether); C₃H₇, 65, 185°/0.6 mm, 118° (benzene-petroleum ether); C₄H₉, 62, 135°/0.4 mm, 121° (benzene-petroleum ether).

Pharmacology: *In vitro* amebicidal activity of IV against *E. histolytica* was carried out at Kalyani University, West Bengal. Minimum inhibitory concentration (μg/ml) of the following compounds (IV) are (n, R₁, R₂, M.I.C. in the order shown) : 3, H, H, 15.8; 3, CH₃, CH₃, 62.5; 3, CH₃, C₂H₅, nil; 3, CH₃, C₂H₇, nil; 3, CH₃, C₄H₉, nil; 4, H, H, 62.5¹¹; 4, CH₃, CH₃, 250.0, while M.I.C. of emetine hydrochloride is 7.87 μg/ml.

From the screening report it appears that the seven membered compounds are less active than the six membered compounds.

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Studies on Antitubercular and Antibacterial Agents: Preparation of 1-(4-Amino benzoyl)-2-benzalhydrazine and 1-[4-(phenylthioureido)benzoyl]-2-substituted-benzalhydrazine

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LITERATURE reveals that a number of studies have been carried out on antitubercular and antibacterial activity of hydrazone and thiourea. Hydrazones have also been found to possess antibacterial^{1,2}, antifungal³ and insecticidal^{4,5} activities. A number of hydrazones have been synthesised through condensation of acid hydrazide with aldehyde and ketone.

The thioureas with various structural modifications are tuberculostatic^{6,7}, anthelmintics⁸, antifungal⁹ and rodenticides¹⁰. We have prepared 1-[4-(phenylthioureido)benzoyl]-2-substituted-benzalhydrazine from various 1-(4-aminobenzoyl)-2-benzalhydrazine by condensation with phenylisothiocyanate and tested against H₃₇R_v strain of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*.

The synthetic sequence of the title compounds is obtained in Scheme 1.

Experimental

4-Aminobenzhydrazide: It was prepared by the reported method¹¹.

1-(4-Aminobenzoyl)-2-benzalhydrazine (II): To the solution of 4-aminobenzhydrazide (0.01 M) in ethanol (95%, 25 ml) added benzaldehyde (0.01 M) in ethanol (95%, 15 ml), content kept for 24 h at room temperature, cooled, filtered, dried and crystallised

NOTES

TABLE 1—DATA OF THE 1-(4-AMINO BENZOYL)-2-BENZAL HYDRAZINE (I)

Sl. no.	R	M.p. °C	Yield %	Antitubercular activity, µg/ml					Antibacterial activity Interpretation of zone of inhibition	
				0.0	25	50	100	150	<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>E. coli</i>
1.	Phenyl	211	87	+	+	+	+	+	-	-
2.	2-Hydroxyphenyl	210	89	+	-	-	-	-	++	-
3.	4-Hydroxyphenyl	250	90	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
4.	Cinnamyl	170	81	+	+	+	+	+	-	-
5.	4-Methoxyphenyl	215	88	+	-	-	+	+	-	-
6.	2-Chlorophenyl	161	84	+	+	+	+	+	-	-
7.	3-Chlorophenyl	225	80	+	+	+	+	+	+	-
8.	3-Nitrophenyl	218	79	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
9.	4-Nitrophenyl	290	75	+	+	+	+	+	+	-
10.	3,4-Methylenedioxyphenyl	266	87	+	-	-	+	+	-	-
11.	4-Hydroxy-3-methoxyphenyl	128	90	+	+	+	-	-	-	+
12.	3,4-Dimethoxyphenyl	252	79	+	+	+	+	+	-	-
13.	3,5-Dibromo-2-hydroxyphenyl	257	88	+	-	-	+	+	+	-
14.	5-Bromo-2-hydroxyphenyl	245	89	+	-	-	-	-	+	-
15.	5-Nitro-4-hydroxy-3-methoxyphenyl	222	79	+	+	+	+	+	-	-
16.	Furfuryl	187	76	+	+	+	+	+	-	-

All the compounds gave satisfactory C, N, S analyses.
 For antitubercular activity : +ve=not active ; -ve=active.
 For antibacterial activity : +ve=active ; -ve=not active.

TABLE 2—DATA OF THE 1-[4-(PHENYLTHIOUREIDO)-BENZOYL]-2-BENZAL HYDRAZINE (II)

Sl. no.	R	M.p. °C	Yield %	Antitubercular activity, µg/ml					Antibacterial activity Interpretation of zone of inhibition	
				0.0	25	50	100	150	<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>E. coli</i>
1.	Phenyl	172	80	+	+	+	+	+	-	-
2.	2-Hydroxyphenyl	295	86	+	-	-	+	+	+	+
3.	4-Hydroxyphenyl	168	88	+	-	-	-	-	+	-
4.	Cinnamyl	176	76	+	+	+	+	+	-	-
5.	4-Methoxyphenyl	195	82	+	+	+	+	+	-	-
6.	2-Chlorophenyl	178	81	+	-	-	+	+	-	-
7.	3-Chlorophenyl	228	72	+	+	-	+	+	-	-
8.	3-Nitrophenyl	150	76	+	+	+	+	+	+	-
9.	4-Nitrophenyl	154	71	+	+	+	+	+	-	-
10.	3,4-Methylenedioxyphenyl	175	78	+	+	+	-	-	-	-
11.	4-Hydroxy-3-methoxyphenyl	199	84	+	+	+	+	+	-	-
12.	3,4-Dimethoxyphenyl	110	75	+	+	+	+	+	-	+
13.	3,5-Dibromo-2-hydroxyphenyl	232	83	+	-	-	+	+	+	+
14.	5-Bromo-2-hydroxyphenyl	164	80	+	-	-	+	+	+	+
15.	5-Nitro-4-hydroxy-3-methoxyphenyl	150	74	+	+	+	+	+	-	-
16.	Furfuryl	203	72	+	+	+	+	+	-	-

Explanation same as in Table 1.

where R= Different aromatic, heterocyclic group.

from ethanol (95%), (87%), m.p. 211° (Found : N, 17.42%. $C_{14}H_{13}N_3O$ requires N, 17.57%).

1-[4-(Phenylthioureido)benzoyl]-2-benzaldehyde hydrazone (II): To the solution of 1-(4-aminobenzoyl)-2-benzaldehyde hydrazone (0.01 M) in dioxan (40 ml) added phenylisothiocyanate (0.01 M) in dioxan (15 ml), contents refluxed for 45 min, cooled and filtered. The product was washed with ether and crystallised from ethanol (95%), (78%), m.p. 172° (Found : N, 14.85 ; S, 8.45%. $C_{21}H_{18}N_4OS$ requires N, 14.9 ; S, 8.55%).

Antimycobacterial screening : The *in vitro* antitubercular activity of the title compounds I and II was studied at 0, 25, 50, 100, 150 µg/ml concentration (solvent DMF) against H₃₇R_v strain of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* using Lowenstein-Jensen medium. The procedure was duplicated with the solvent for control purpose.

Antibacterial screening : The antibacterial activity of the title compounds I and II was studied

against *E. coli* and *S. aureus*. The disk concentration of 100 µg/disk of all the compounds have been prepared using DMF as solvent.

The physical data of the compounds are recorded in Table 1 and 2. The ir spectra of thiourea, where R=2-hydroxyphenyl show band at 1380 cm⁻¹ due to -NH-CS-NH- linkage and characteristic band at 3200 cm⁻¹ suggesting the presence of stretching vibration of OH group of salicylaldehyde moiety.

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Possible Antifertility Agents. Part-I. Synthesis of 2-(N,N-Substituted-aminomethyl)-3-(2-pyridyl)-4(3H)-oxo-3,1-quinazolines

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SEVERAL quinazoline-4-one derivatives have been reported¹⁻³ to exhibit appreciable antifertility activity. Similarly, other heterocyclic systems with basic amine residues were also reported⁴⁻⁶ to exert antifertility action. Therefore, it was considered worthwhile to synthesise 2-(N,N-substituted aminomethyl)-3-(2-pyridyl)-4(3H)-oxo-3,1-quinazolines which incorporated these structural features (Scheme 1) and to study their antifertility action.

Scheme 1

Experimental

M.ps. were determined in open capillary tubes and uncorrected. Infrared spectra of the compounds were recorded on a Perkin Elmer 137 infracord and Perkin Elmer 177 grating instruments. The pmr spectra were recorded on Perkin Elmer R-3 spectrometer (90 MHz) in CDCl₃ and the chemical shift values are expressed in δ units using TMS as an internal standard.

2-Nitro-benz(2-pyridyl)amide (I): 2-Aminopyridine (1.88 g, 0.02 mol) and 2-nitrobenzoyl chloride (3.71 g, 0.02 mol) were refluxed in dry benzene in presence of triethylamine (6 ml, 0.04 mol) for 10 h (tlc). Triethylamine hydrochloride separated out was filtered and the filtrate on concentration yielded the crude amide which was recrystallised from ethanol (3.0 g, 62%), m.p. 150-52° (Found: N, 17.29%. C₁₃H₉N₃O₃ requires N, 17.28%); ν_{max} (KBr) 1350 and 1535 (N=O), 1595 (C=C), 1700 (C=O) and 3400 cm⁻¹ (NH stretching).

2-Amino-benz(2-pyridyl)amide (II): Hydrazine hydrate (40 ml) was carefully added to a solution of amide (I) (2.40 g, 0.01 mol) in methanol (50 ml) containing Raney nickel (0.5 g) for 4 h at room temperature. Then catalyst was filtered off and the filtrate was concentrated to obtain the product (1.5 g, 70%), m.p. 130-31° (lit.⁷ 132-33°) (Found: N, 19.75%. C₁₃H₁₁N₃O requires N, 19.72%); ν_{max} (KBr) 1595 (C=C), 1680 (C=O) and 3300, 3400 cm⁻¹ (NH). The absence of peaks at 1380 and